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A STUDY OF EXPERIENCES WITH DISTANCE AND ONLINE TEACHING IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Due to the university lockdown caused by COVID-19, teachers and students at the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark experienced a sudden and massive change from face-to-face to distance and online teaching in spring 2020. To obtain an overview of the tools used for online teaching and the experiences gained, the department conducted a survey among its teachers. This questionnaire consisted of two key questions: “What worked well?” and “What worked less well?”. A second survey containing similar questions was conducted by the university among all students.

A qualitative analysis of the empirical data generated by the surveys provides an overview of the teaching tools and methods used after the forced conversion to distance and online teaching. The analysis illuminates the strengths and weaknesses of the different teaching methods, from both teachers’ and students’ perspectives. Based on the findings, recommendations are made to support teachers as they guide students towards learning strategies that best fit the chosen teaching methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) was locked down in spring 2020. Overnight, teachers and students experienced a massive emergency change in teaching and learning, away from physical, face-to-

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face to distance and online activities. This new online teaching environment had two important characteristics: first, most teachers had little or no experience and were left with no guidelines or support from the university. Second, it was unknown how long this situation would last - a week, a month or longer? Thus, teachers were left to their own devices and had to transition their courses relying only on their traditional teaching experiences.

The purpose of this research is to collect experiences with emergency online teaching from both teachers' and students' perspectives, and to analyse these experiences to find out what worked well and what worked less well. Going forward, the old ways of teaching, based purely on physical attendance, will likely be replaced by a hybrid model that combines online and in person education. It is therefore important to learn from these experiences, and thus, this research focuses on two questions:

- Which issues can be observed with respect to emergency distance and online teaching?
- What practices should be implemented into teaching when transitioning to a hybrid model?

1.1 Related work

The massive emergency change to online teaching and learning caused by COVID-19 was a novel, worldwide experience. Although online teaching and learning is not new, transitioning to an online format was prior to COVID-19 typically a well-planned activity. However, in spring 2020, the lockdown of colleges and universities and the ensuing change to online teaching and learning was anything but well-planned. Planning, preparing, and developing an online university course typically takes months. In March 2020, the term emergency remote teaching (ERT) was introduced to distinguish between teaching and learning that was planned and designed to be online, and the temporary shift to an alternate mode in response to the crisis [1].

Online teaching and learning has been studied for decades, and numerous well-planned transformations to online formats are described in existing literature. However, research related to COVID-19 emergency online changes is more limited. Additionally, different foci are presented. While [2] reflects on the crisis-response migration methods employed by universities, students and faculty members, the questionnaire-based case study with 44 teachers in mechanical engineering at a vocational high school in Indonesia, [3], focuses on learning strategies, platforms, and instructional media during a pandemic. Only few case studies exist on teachers' and students' perception of the emergency online teaching and learning during university lockdowns. For example, in an interview-based case study with 12 faculty members and 12 students from University College of Medicine and University College of Dentistry, Lahore, Pakistan, [4] explores the perception of teachers and students regarding advantages, limitations and recommendations with ERT. The case study in [5] is based on interviews with 11 undergraduate engineering students at University of San Diego, USA, and investigates the methods students used to

adapt to remote learning, and what faculty can do to support students during ERT. The case study in [6] is based on an anonymous survey with 183 participants from a Midwestern university in the U.S. Quantitative data analysis is used to examine faculty members' perceptions of online teaching during the pandemic and their satisfaction with the transition.

In this paper, we focus on the perceptions of both faculty members and students in courses taught in spring 2020 at the Department of Mechanical Engineering at DTU.

1.2 The research aim

The aim of this research is twofold. Based on the generated empirical data the first aim is to create an overview of the different teaching methods used, and to identify the strengths and weaknesses. Based on these findings, the second aim is to make recommendations that support teachers as they guide students towards learning strategies that best fit the chosen teaching methods. Students use different learning strategies; some students use a deep learning strategy while others use surface learning [7]. Teachers' awareness of both strategies is relevant not only in the context of traditional face-to-face teaching but also in emergency teaching and learning as well as when transitioning to a hybrid model that combines online and in person education.

2 RESEARCH METHOD

The present exploratory study is based on a qualitative research approach. The empirical data for this study were generated through two questionnaires. First, the Department of Mechanical Engineering emailed a questionnaire to the teachers in the department. This questionnaire contained two key questions: "What worked well?" and "What worked less well?". Answers from teachers of approximately 40 mechanical engineering courses were collected through this survey. Second, a university-wide questionnaire was sent to all students focusing on teaching during the university lockdown. This questionnaire included two key questions: "What has worked well? Please tell us about any positive aspects of on-line teaching that you think DTU can use in the future", and "What did not work well? Please tell us about aspects of on-line teaching that could be improved" The answers from students who in spring 2020 participated in mechanical engineering courses were thereby collected. Next, these data were added to two documents listing what worked well and what worked less well. Statements from teachers were coloured blue and statements from students were coloured red to easily distinguish between the different perspectives.

In total, the two questionnaires resulted in 251 statements concerning mechanical engineering courses. This included 39 statements from teachers regarding what worked well, and 49 statements what worked less well. Also included are 91 statements from students regarding what worked well, and 72 statements what worked less well. Since 251 statements distributed across 40 courses do not say much about the teaching in each individual course, the research team decided to

structure the empirical data through a bottom-up process with the help of an affinity diagram [8]. The statements were first printed on individual paper slips and mixed up. Next, the statements were read carefully and similar statements were grouped. Finally, each group was given a title reflecting the theme of the grouped statements. Figure 1 shows a picture of the affinity diagram in its making.

Figure 1. The affinity diagram in its making. Some themes have already emerged: Social dimension, time consumption, skips examples, video lectures etc.

From the affinity diagram it was possible to create a rich picture of the experiences seen from both the teachers' and students' perspectives. It was not the intention to use statistical methods to analyse these statements, because it is not the frequency of single statements that is of interest, but the richness of the picture.

3 RESULTS

The following themes emerged from the affinity diagram: Online lectures (synchronous learning), Video lectures (asynchronous learning), Group work and supervision, E-mail supervision, Teaching assistant (TA), Videos explaining answers to previous exams (asynchronous learning), Time consumption/Time management, The social dimension, No transportation, Lack of physical materials/models, Technical issues incl. software tools.

3.1 Overview of software tools used

At DTU, teachers and students had to transform to the online format overnight, and neither guidelines nor support were available. Thus, the teachers began teaching online based on their individual experiences, and the software tools listed by the teachers reflect many different choices as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Software tools chosen by the teachers

Teaching method	Software tools
Online streaming (synchronous learning)	Zoom, Skype, Teams
Pre-recorded lectures (asynchronous learning)	pdf-files with voice over, YouTube videos, Adobe Connect
Lectures without voice/self-study (asynchronous learning)	PowerPoint slides
Supervision	e-mail, Piazza.com, Discord, Mural

The multiplicity of software tools used was not necessarily viewed positively by the students. For example, two students wrote:

- *“It was annoying that two different platforms were used for this.”*
- *“...Also an absolute MUST is for the teachers to use a unified streaming platform. We have been using 3 different ones during the semester and that is not good. Zoom seems nice, but Discord/Microsoft Teams is also nice for group work.”*

3.2 Observations of live streaming lectures

With respect to synchronous live streaming of lectures, some teachers reported that it was difficult to sense students' reaction. For example, two teachers wrote:

- *“It was difficult to see the reactions of the students, so it is a bit difficult to judge whether there is a good response from the students. There is no feedback during the lecture itself.”*
- *“It is difficult to sense whether the students received the teaching as intended - when asked, it was typically the same student who answered.”*

However synchronous live streaming may help students' motivation as the following four student statements suggest:

- *“Holding LIVE lectures online has been really good! It keeps you motivated to do what you have to do and participate in the course each week, so you do not fall behind / postpone it.”*
- *“Worked really well with Skype teaching especially because there could be a communication between lecturer and students. Also mildly “forced” one to follow the normal schedule rhythm because it [the lecture] was not [recorded]”*
- *“It seemed good that the teacher was very aware of whether those who followed had understood the material correctly... both by stopping and asking if you are involved, but also asking academic questions to the students”*
- *“The drawback is you cannot ask direct questions during the course. You still have the opportunity to ask questions, but it cannot be compared to the lecture being conducted in person”*

3.3 Observations of recorded video lectures

Some teachers reported positive feedback from the students when lectures were pre-recorded for asynchronous use. For example, two teachers wrote:

- *“There was positive feedback about the digital lectures. They were happy to have the opportunity to use them at their own pace”*
- *“Audio-annotated lecture slides. (The majority of the feedback from the students on these has been very positive)”*

However, both positive and negative feedback regarding video lectures was received, and two students wrote:

- *“Audio annotations for teaching slides were good as they could be heard again.”*
- *“I was not good at keeping up when the teaching worked as it did having PowerPoints with speak. I found it difficult to get involved in this form of teaching. I therefore made all previous exam sets instead.”*

The students were not able to ask questions during recorded video lectures and some found it difficult to engage in teaching as these four student statements suggest:

- *“The videos do not allow you to ask questions during the lecture.”*
- *“It has been really good with the videos - especially when you have been able to rewind and hear something an extra time if you did not get a detail. I would always prefer to get physical education, but to be honest I almost think I have benefited more from watching the videos rather than blackboard teaching (if the exact same thing was said). The downside is of course that you cannot ask for details. Of course you can write an email, but it just seems cumbersome and heavy.”*
- *“Honestly, I thought that the online teaching was way too easy. - Just following a video step by step reminds me of being a little kid trying to learn different software by watching YouTube videos.”*
- *“Online teaching is a bit like a cheap copy of coca cola. It's a second rank version of the real cola. One can perfect the recipe as much as one wants, but the "secret ingredient" is the physical attendance, one cannot imitate and the quality of teaching will be markedly inferior!”*

The possibility of choosing their individual time schedule when viewing the recorded lectures was received positively by some, as two students wrote:

- *“What worked the best was not having to wake up super early and saving money not having to drive two hours a day...”*
- *“Offhand, the only advantage is that you have been able to adapt the teaching to your own scheduling”*

3.4 Observations of e-mail supervision

Some teachers considered e-mail as an open invitation to ask questions that students could easily use. Thus, two teachers wrote:

- *“Mail correspondence with the students. I have the impression that those who wrote felt well helped, and I have been happy for that source of contact.”*
- *“The (most) students who made use of the offer took the time to formulate their questions well so that it was (relatively) easy to give a good answer.”*

However, the students did not have the same perception regarding the ease of formulating questions in writing, e-mailing the teacher, and receiving a helpful answer. Three students wrote:

- *“I missed having the TA being present for help after the lectures. It is more difficult to describe your questions via mail and you also hesitate more to ask.”*
- *“On the other hand, the course form is difficult in online format, because often questions regarding assignments are best clarified by drawing and discussing rather than writing over the web.”*
- *“It was really hard to conduct the exercises, since the teachers would not answer to emails (we had to send the same email multiple times until we got a not really satisfying/helpful answer)...”*

3.5 Observations of time consumption

The only theme where students and teachers seemed to agree was time consumption. Both parties considered emergency online teaching to be more time consuming than physical, face-to-face teaching.

Two teachers wrote:

- *“Much more time has been spent on supervision than I usually do because it takes longer to explain than when sitting next to each other.”*
- *“Video lectures take a lot of time and provide no interaction with the students. Digital whiteboard with a tablet is difficult to use compared to a physical whiteboard.”*

Five students wrote:

- *“I do not think online teaching can replace real [face-to-face] teaching. I use a lot of asking questions, and learn a lot from it, but there was not the same opportunity for it online ... Several times I experienced that what I wrote was misunderstood, and it would be done much faster in reality [face-to-face]”*
- *“I really liked the online course content on YouTube. All the small details you would miss in class, you had right in front of you. This said, the analysis of each lecture took a lot more time than normal. Personally I have spent 4-6 hours on each lecture, as you have a tendency to stop and play all the time. This is without the time spent on the exercises.”*

- *“The only negative aspect was that it increased around 30% the time to dedicate to the subject, it took on average 3.5 hours to “translate” in notes the lectures”*
- *“... Also not to stereotype, but it might be that a lot of engineering students are dyslexic, me for instance, reading is therefore highly time consuming task compared to lectures...”*
- *“The delays in the lectures, together with the lecturer clearly being on the verge of collapse with stress!”*

4 DISCUSSION

The involuntary transformation to online teaching in spring 2020 was a novel experience for everyone. The present study shows that both teachers and students found emergency remote teaching more challenging and problematic than face-to-face teaching. First, the use of multiple software tools was frustrating for some students. Second, the new format required more time from both teachers and students. Some teachers used more time on supervision and preparing lectures, while some students used more time on formulating questions in writing, revisiting lectures and creating notes by transcribing online content.

A strength of pre-recorded video lectures is that students can review the content when it is convenient for them and at their own pace. Weaknesses are a lack of interaction with teachers and fellow students, and that students may end up focusing on details rather than the overall content and structure of the lecture.

Strengths of live streamed lectures are that teachers and students can interact in real time, and that students are required to follow a scheduled timeline, providing structure for their studies. A weakness of lectures that are only live streamed and not recorded is that they cannot be revisited by students for clarifying difficult details at a later time. Additionally, students may be reluctant to ask questions online as they may need to leave their comfort zone in order to interact with others.

From the teachers' perspective, e-mail support may have been seen as an open invitation for students to ask questions. However, students found it difficult to formulate questions when they did not understand an assignment or felt they had limited knowledge about a subject.

The study's observations from teachers and students should be considered as universities adopt hybrid teaching that combines online and in person education. Departments could agree on a few common software tools that are used across all courses as use of multiple software tools was found to cause students' frustration. We recommend e-mail supervision replaced by online Q&A sessions to give students the option to ask questions orally and allow other students to benefit from the discussion as well. Regardless of whether teachers choose pre-recorded or live-streamed lectures, the chosen methods' strengths and weaknesses should be discussed with students to help guide them towards learning strategies that best fit those methods.

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